

```
[      1      11      21      31      41      51      61      71      81      91      ]
[
Dd636   ATGTATCTTTTAGTTTTGTTTTCCCTTTAATTGGGGCGGTTTTAGTTGGTTCTTTTGGACGAAAAATAGGGGAAAGGGTGCTGGTGTTTAACTTCCT
Dd432   .....
Lp_KC875348 .....A.....
Lp_KC875349 .....A.....
Lp_FR821799 .....A.....
ChangesNS .....N.....
```

```
[     101     111     121     131     141     151     161     171     181     191     ]
[
Dd636   GTTGTTTAATTATAAGTCTTCTTATTCTGTTTTTATTGGGGCAGAAATTTATTTAACTCAACAATAACATATATTAAGTTGTGAAAGTGATTTGATTC
Dd432   .....C.....
Lp_KC875348 .....
Lp_KC875349 .....
Lp_FR821799 .....
ChangesNS .....S.....
```

```
[     201     211     221     231     241     251     261     271     281     291     ]
[
Dd636   AGGATCTTTCCTTGTTTTTTTTGGTTTACAATTTGATTGTTTAGTTGTGATTATGTTGTTTGTGTTTTATTGTTTCTACTTTGGTTCATATTTTTTCT
Dd432   .....
Lp_KC875348 .....
Lp_KC875349 .....
Lp_FR821799 .....
ChangesNS .....S.....
```

```
[     301     311     321     331     341     351     361     371     381     391     ]
[
Dd636   ATTGCCCTACATGCGAGGAGATCCCCATGTCCACGGTTATGTCTTATCTTTCTTTGTTTACTTTTTTAATGGTTGTTTGTAGTAACAAGTGATAATTCC
Dd432   .....T.....
Lp_KC875348 .....
Lp_KC875349 .....
Lp_FR821799 .....
ChangesNS .....S.....
```

```
[     401     411     421     431     441     451     461     471     481     491     ]
[
Dd636   TTCAGTTATTTATTGGCTGGGAGGGGGTAGGCCCTTGTCTTATTTATTAATTAATTTTGGATTAACAAGATTAGAAGCAAACAGAGCTGCGATTAAAGC
Dd432   .....G.....
Lp_KC875348 .....
Lp_KC875349 .....
Lp_FR821799 .....
ChangesNS .....N.....
```

```
[          501          511          521          531          541          551          561          571          581          591          ]
[          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          ]
Dd636      AATGTTAGTAAATCGAGTGGGGACATTGGGTTGCTTTTAGCAATGTTTCTTATTTGAAATGTTTTTGGGACCTTAGACTTTTCTTCTGTTTTTAATTTA
Dd432      .....
Lp_KC875348 .....
Lp_KC875349 .....
Lp_FR821799 .....
ChangesNS  .....
```

```
[          601          611          621          631          641          651          661          671          681          691          ]
[          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          ]
Dd636      GTTTTTGTGTTCTGATCAAATTTTTTTTATTTGTTTATTCTTGTCTTAGGAGTGGTTGGTAAATCGGCTCAATGGGGCTACACACTTGATTACCGG
Dd432      .....G.....
Lp_KC875348 .....G.....
Lp_KC875349 .....G.....
Lp_FR821799 .....G.....
ChangesNS  .....S.....
```

```
[          701          711          721          731          741          751          761          771          781          791          ]
[          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          ]
Dd636      ATGCAATGGAAGGTTAGTTGGGCCTTTTAATTAATAAAATTAATTAATAAACGCCACTATGATTATAAAAGCTTTCGTTGTTCTTGTCCCTTTACTTATTGC
Dd432      .....T.....
Lp_KC875348 .....T.....
Lp_KC875349 .....T.....
Lp_FR821799 .....T.....
ChangesNS  .....S.....
```

```
[          801          811          821          831          841          851          861          871          881          891          ]
[          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          ]
Dd636      TGTGGCATATTTAACTTTAGCAGAACGAAAGTTTTAGGGTACATGCAAGCAAGAAAAGGACCTAATGTGGTTGGGGGGGNTTGCTTCAGCCTTTTGCG
Dd432      .....G.....
Lp_KC875348 .....G.....
Lp_KC875349 .....G.....
Lp_FR821799 .....G.....
ChangesNS  .....S.....
```

```
[          901          911          921          931          941          951          961          971          981          991          ]
[          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          ]
Dd636      GATGGGATTAAGTTATTTCTTAAAGAAATGGTTATTTCCCATCGAGTGAGTGGGTTTGTATTCTTTTAGCCCCAGTCTTTCTTTTATTTTGGCTTTTA
Dd432      .....
Lp_KC875348 .....
Lp_KC875349 .....
Lp_FR821799 .....
ChangesNS  .....
```

```
[      1001      1011      1021      1031      1041      1051      1061      1071      1081      1091      ]
[
Dd636      TTGTTTGGGGTATCCTCCCTTATAATAAGGGGGTTGGAATAAGTGATTTTCAAATTTGGTCTTTTATGAATCATGGCGATTTCTTCTGTGAGTGTATATGC
Dd432      .....A.....
Lp_KC875348 .....T.....A.....
Lp_KC875349 .....T.....A.....
Lp_FR821799 .....T.....A.....
ChangesNS .....S.....N.....
```

```
[      1101      1111      1121      1131      1141      1151      1161      1171      1181      1191      ]
[
Dd636      TATTTTAATGTCGGGCTGAGGCAGTCGTTCTAAATATGCTTTTTTAGGTGCGGTCCGAGCTGCGGCGCAAATGATTAGTTATGAGGTTTCTATTGGTTTA
Dd432      .....
Lp_KC875348 .....
Lp_KC875349 .....
Lp_FR821799 .....
ChangesNS .....

```

```
[      1201      1211      1221      1231      1241      1251      1261      1271      1281      1291      ]
[
Dd636      ATTATTATTCTGTTCTTTTATGTGTGGGTCTTTGTCTTTAAATGAAATTGTATTAACACAAAATGAAATTTGGTTTTTTTTTCCCTTTTCTCCTGTG
Dd432      .....G.....
Lp_KC875348 .....
Lp_KC875349 .....
Lp_FR821799 .....G.....
ChangesNS .....N.....

```

```
[      1301      1311      1321      1331      1341      1351      1361      1371      1381      1391      ]
[
Dd636      TTATAATGTTWCTCGTTTCTATTTTAGCAGAAACAAACCGTGCTCCCTTTGATTTAACARAAGGAGAGTCGGAGCTRGTGTCGGGGTACAACGTAGAGTA
Dd432      .....T.....G.....A.....
Lp_KC875348 .....T.....G.....A.....
Lp_KC875349 .....T.....G.....A.....
Lp_FR821799 .....T.....G.....A.....
ChangesNS .....S.....S.....S.....

```

```
[      1401      1411      1421      1431      1441      1451      1461      1471      1481      1491      ]
[
Dd636      CGCTTCGATGCTTTTTGCTCTATTTTTTCTTGCCGAATATGCTCATATTATATTTATGAGTTGTTTAACTGTTCTTTTATTTTTTGGAGGATGGTTGCTT
Dd432      .....
Lp_KC875348 .....
Lp_KC875349 .....
Lp_FR821799 .....
ChangesNS .....

```

```
[      1501      1511      1521      1531      1541      1551      1561      1571      1581      1591      ]
[
Dd636      TTGCCCTTGGTTTTAAACCGTTTTTATGTTTTATTTTTTTATGGGCACGGGCCCTTTCCCTAGGGTCCGGTATGATCAATTGATGGYCCTATTAT
Dd432      .....C.....
Lp_KC875348 .....C.....
Lp_KC875349 .....C.....
Lp_FR821799 .....C.....
ChangesNS .....S.....
```

```
[      1601      1611      1621      1631      1641      1651      1661      1671      1681      1691      ]
[
Dd636      GAAAGGGTATTTACCTTTAAGTTTAGGGATTGTTATTTTGTGGCCAGTATTTTATTCGGGTTTAATGGTTCTCCTCCG---ATGAGTGGTGCTTATTT
Dd432      .....ATT.....
Lp_KC875348 .....ATT.....
Lp_KC875349 .....ATT.....
Lp_FR821799 .....ATT.....
ChangesNS .....---
```

```
[      1701      1711      1721      1731      1741      1751      1761      1771      1781      1791      ]
[
Dd636      TGATCAATTTAATATTGTGTGATTATTTGGTGTGACGAACTCGGCAGTAATGATGGGCCTTACAGTTATTATTGTTTTATTGTTTTTAAATGGGGTGGAT
Dd432      .....
Lp_KC875348 .....
Lp_KC875349 .....
Lp_FR821799 .....
ChangesNS .....

```

```
[      1801      1811      1821      1831      1841      1851      1861      1871      1881      1891      ]
[
Dd636      CTCATCCCAAAAAGATGGCAATCTATTTTAGAGTTAACATATAGTCATTTTATCGTGTATAGAAGACAATYTTGGGAGGGGAGGGGTTGAAGTATTTCT
Dd432      .....T.....
Lp_KC875348 .....T.....
Lp_KC875349 .....T.....
Lp_FR821799 .....T.....
ChangesNS .....S.....
```

```
[      1901      1911      1921      1931      1941      1951      1961      1971      1981      1991      ]
[
Dd636      CTTTTGTTCTCTCTTTTTTTCTTTGGGGTTTGTGTTGAATGTGCTGGGTTTATGCCCATATGTTTTTACTCCAACCGTTCATATTATAGTTACATTGGG
Dd432      .....N.....
Lp_KC875348 .....
Lp_KC875349 .....
Lp_FR821799 .....
ChangesNS .....S.....
```

```
[      2001      2011      2021      2031      2041      2051      2061      2071      2081      2091      ]
[      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      ]
Dd636   TTTATCTTTTCAATAATCATCGGTGTCACCTCTTGCTGGTTTTTGGAGGTTTAAAGTGAGATTTTTTTAGTGTTTTTATGCCAAGCGGAGCCCCTCTGGG
Dd432   .....
Lp_KC875348 .....
Lp_KC875349 .....
Lp_FR821799 .....
ChangesNS .....
```

```
[      2101      2111      2121      2131      2141      2151      2161      2171      2181      2191      ]
[      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      ]
Dd636   CTTGCCCTTTGTTAGTTTAAATTGAAACAGTTAGTTATATCTCACGGGCTATTTTCGTTAGGAGTTCGTTTGGCGGCTAATTTATCGGCTGGGCATCTAT
Dd432   .....
Lp_KC875348 .....
Lp_KC875349 .....
Lp_FR821799 .....
ChangesNS .....
```

```
[      2201      2211      2221      2231      2241      2251      2261      2271      2281      2291      ]
[      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      ]
Dd636   TATTTGCTATTTTAGCTGGGTTTGGGTTTAAATATGTTAATTGCAAGTGGGCCGGCGGGCTATTGCCCTTGTTAATAATGGTTTTTATAACACTATTAGA
Dd432   .....
Lp_KC875348 .....G.....
Lp_KC875349 .....G.....
Lp_FR821799 .....G.....
ChangesNS .....S.....
```

```
[      2301      2311      2321      2331      2341      2351      2361      2371      2381      2391      ]
[      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      ]
Dd636   AGTGGCGGTGGCCGTAATTCAGGCTTATGTTTTTGTATTATTAACAACACTATTTATTAGCAGACACTGATTTTACATATGGGTCTTTTTTGGCTAGTT
Dd432   .....
Lp_KC875348 .....
Lp_KC875349 .....
Lp_FR821799 .....
ChangesNS .....
```

```
[      2401      2411      2421      2431      2441      2451      2461      2471      2481      2491      ]
[      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      ]
Dd636   CTTTTTGTGGGATCATAAGTGTGACGGGGCTTCAAGAGAAAAAAGGAGTGTGTTAAAAAACGGGCTTAGAGTGATCTATGGCTATTTTTTTTAGCT
Dd432   .....
Lp_KC875348 .....
Lp_KC875349 .....
Lp_FR821799 .....
ChangesNS .....
```

```
[      2501      2511      2521      2531      2541      2551      2561      2571      2581      2591      ]
[
Dd636      CTTTAGTTTGTGGGGCGGATTTGACTGAGAAGGACATTTTCAATTTATTCATCAAATAGAATGAGAAATGCTTTTTATCTTGGACTGAGGCCCTATTAT
Dd432      .....
Lp_KC875348 .....
Lp_KC875349 .....
Lp_FR821799 .....
ChangesNS .....

```

```
[      2601      2611      2621      2631      2641      2651      2661      2671      2681      2691      ]
[
Dd636      TTTTGCCTTGGATGGTGTTCCTTGTTTTTTTTGGCTTTTAACAACTTTTTAATACCGATTTGTGTTTTAATCAGTCAAAAATCTATCCGGTTTTTTATTT
Dd432      .....
Lp_KC875348 .....T.
Lp_KC875349 .....T.
Lp_FR821799 .....T.
ChangesNS .....S.

```

```
[      2701      2711      2721      2731      2741      2751      2761      2771      2781      2791      ]
[
Dd636      AAAGAATTCCTTTTATGTTTATTTTTTTTGTAGAGTGTTTTAGTCGGTGTGTTTTTGGTGTGTTGATCTCTTTTATTTTATATTTTTTTTGGAGGGATTT
Dd432      .....
Lp_KC875348 .....
Lp_KC875349 .....
Lp_FR821799 .....
ChangesNS .....

```

```
[      2801      2811      2821      2831      2841      2851      2861      2871      2881      2891      ]
[
Dd636      TAATCCCAATGTTCTTTTAAATTGGAATTTGGGGTCCCAGAGAAGAAAAGGTTTCGCGCTCTTTTTATTTTTTTTTTTTTCNNACTTTGCGGGTCCGT
Dd432      .....
Lp_KC875348 .....
Lp_KC875349 .....
Lp_FR821799 .....
ChangesNS .....

```

```
[      2901      2911      2921      2931      2941      2951      2961      2971      2981      2991      ]
[
Dd636      GTTTTTTTTTTTACAATCCTTTTTTTGTATCGAACACAGGGGCAACAGATTATTTCTTTTGCTTAATCTTAGGCTGTCTCCCAATGTTGAGAAGTGG
Dd432      .....
Lp_KC875348 .....
Lp_KC875349 .....
Lp_FR821799 .....
ChangesNS .....

```

```
[      3001      3011      3021      3031      3041      3051      3061      3071      3081      3091      ]
[      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      ]
Dd636   GCCTTAATTGGCGTCTTTCTTAGTTTTGCAGTTAAAATCCCTTAATCCCGTTTCATATTTGGCTTCCCAAGCACATGTGGAAGCCCTGTTGCGGGCT
Dd432   .....
Lp_KC875348 .....
Lp_KC875349 .....
Lp_FR821799 .....
ChangesNS .....
```

```
[      3101      3111      3121      3131      3141      3151      3161      3171      3181      3191      ]
[      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      ]
Dd636   CAGTTATTTTAGCTGGGATTTTATTAATAACTAGGGGGGTATGGGGTTTTACGGTTTTCTTGGCCTCTCTCCCTGCGGCTTCTGAATATTGATCTCCTGT
Dd432   .....C.....
Lp_KC875348 .....
Lp_KC875349 .....
Lp_FR821799 .....
ChangesNS .....
```

```
[      3201      3211      3221      3231      3241      3251      3261      3271      3281      3291      ]
[      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      ]
Dd636   TATTGTTTTTTTTCTGWTTTGGCYGTTGTTTATGGGGTTTAAATGACATGTCGTCAGGTTGACTTTAAACGACTAGTTGCTTATTCTTCGGTGGCACAC
Dd432   .....T.....T.....
Lp_KC875348 .....T.....T.....
Lp_KC875349 .....T.....T.....
Lp_FR821799 .....T.....T.....
ChangesNS .....S.....S.....
```

```
[      3301      3311      3321      3331      3341      3351      3361      3371      3381      3391      ]
[      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      ]
Dd636   ATGGGTTTAGTTCCTCTAGGGGTTTTACACATATTATAGAAGGGCTTGTGGAGCTGTTTTTTTAAATGTTAGCCCATGGTTTTGTAGTTCGGCTCTTT
Dd432   .....CC.....
Lp_KC875348 .....C.....
Lp_KC875349 .....C.....
Lp_FR821799 .....C.....
ChangesNS .....SS.....
```

```
[      3401      3411      3421      3431      3441      3451      3461      3471      3481      3491      ]
[      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      ]
Dd636   TTATTGGGATTACGTATTTATATGATCGCCATCATACTCGTTTAAATTAATATTTATCGTGGCTTGGCTTTAACGATGCCGCTTTTTGCTATTTCAATGTT
Dd432   .....
Lp_KC875348 .....
Lp_KC875349 .....
Lp_FR821799 .....
ChangesNS .....
```

```
[          3501          3511          3521          3531          3541          3551          3561          3571          3581          3591          ]
[
Dd636      | AATTTTGTCC|TTAACAAACATGGGCTTCCCGTTAAGTAGTAATTTTGTGGAGAGTTTTTTTCTTTGTTAGCAGCTTTTAAGTATCATTTGGGGGTTGGG
Dd432      | .....Y.....
Lp_KC875348| .....
Lp_KC875349| .....
Lp_FR821799| .....
ChangesNS  | .....S.....
```

```
[          3601          3611          3621          3631          3641          3651          3661          3671          3681          3691          ]
[
Dd636      | GGTTTTGTGTTT|TAGGAGTTATTTTTTCTGTTGTTTATCTCTTAGTTTGTTTAWTCGGATTTCTTTTGGGGYGGTTCTAATTATCTTCTTTTAAACA
Dd432      | .....A.....C.....
Lp_KC875348| .....A.....C.....
Lp_KC875349| .....A.....C.....
Lp_FR821799| .....A.....C.....
ChangesNS  | .....S.....S.....
```

```
[          3701          3711          3721          3731          3741          3751          3761          3771          3781          3791          ]
[
Dd636      | GAGATTTAAGTCGACAAGAAGCTTTTGTGCATGCTTCCTTTTCTTGTAATATTTTTTTTGGGGCGTTGTCCCTTTTTTTATTCTTGATTTAATAAGAAA
Dd432      | .....
Lp_KC875348| .....
Lp_KC875349| .....
Lp_FR821799| .....
ChangesNS  | .....
```

```
[          3801          3811          3821          3831          3841          3851          3861          3871          3881          3891          ]
[
Dd636      | TTGTCTTGTTT|TAGTCCGATTGGATATGACTATCATCTTGTGGAGTTTCTCCTTGACCTTTTATTGGAGCTGCCGGGGCCTTCTTCTGACTGTGGGG
Dd432      | .....
Lp_KC875348| .....
Lp_KC875349| .....
Lp_FR821799| .....
ChangesNS  | .....
```

```
[          3901          3911          3921          3931          3941          3951          3961          3971          3981          3991          ]
[
Dd636      | GCAGTTGTTTTT|TTCATTATGGTTTGACTTTTTTTTTGGGTTTAGGGCGCTGATTGTA|CTTGGGGTGATGTTTGTTTGATGACAAGACATTATACGAG
Dd432      | .....
Lp_KC875348| .....
Lp_KC875349| .....
Lp_FR821799| .....
ChangesNS  | .....
```

```
[      4001      4011      4021      4031      4041      4051      4061      4071      4081      4091      ]
[
Dd636   |AAGCGACTTTTCAGGGACACCATTCTTTAGTTGTAAAGCAAGGCCTTAAGTATGGCATGCTTTTGTTTATTCTTTCAGAAGTTTTGTTTTTTTTTCTTT
Dd432   |.....
Lp_KC875348 |.....
Lp_KC875349 |.....
Lp_FR821799 |.....
ChangesNS |.....
```

```
[      4101      4111      4121      4131      4141      4151      4161      4171      4181      4191      ]
[
Dd636   |TTTTTGAGCTTTTTTTCATAGTAGTTGGCTCCGGCTATGAACTTGGGGTGTGTGACCACCGCAAGGTGTTTCATGCGCTAAATCCTTTTTCTGTCCA
Dd432   |.....
Lp_KC875348 |.....
Lp_KC875349 |.....
Lp_FR821799 |.....
ChangesNS |.....
```

```
[      4201      4211      4221      4231      4241      4251      4261      4271      4281      4291      ]
[
Dd636   |TTGTTAAGCACGGCCGTTTATTGAGTTCTGGGGCATCGGTAACGTGGGCCCATCATGCTATAATAAGTGGGAATAAGAAAGAAGCCGTTGCAGGTTTGT
Dd432   |.....A.....G.....
Lp_KC875348 |.....A.....
Lp_KC875349 |.....A.....
Lp_FR821799 |.....A.....
ChangesNS |.....N.....N.....
```

```
[      4301      4311      4321      4331      4341      4351      4361      4371      4381      4391      ]
[
Dd636   |CTTTGACTATTTTATTGGGTGTGGTGTTCACAGGTTTACAGGCCCTTGAATATTATGAAGCTCCCTTGGCTCTTCCGATTCTGTTTATGGCTCCACTTT
Dd432   |.....C.....
Lp_KC875348 |.....
Lp_KC875349 |.....
Lp_FR821799 |.....
ChangesNS |.....S.....
```

```
[      4401      4411      4421      4431      4441      4451      4461      4471      4481      4491      ]
[
Dd636   |TTTTGTGCAACAGGTTTCATGGGTTACACGTGATAATGGAACAACTTTTTGTGTTGTTGTTTCTTCGGTTACTTCCAATCAGTTTACCCGTAGC
Dd432   |.....
Lp_KC875348 |.....G..
Lp_KC875349 |.....G..
Lp_FR821799 |.....G..
ChangesNS |.....N..
```

```
[      4501      4511      4521      4531      4541      4551      4561      4571      4581      4591      ]
[
Dd636      CAACATCTGGGTTTTGAAGCGGCAAGTTGATATTGGCATTTTGTTCGATGTTGTTTGGTTGTTTTTATATCTTTCAATTTATTTGTGGGGTTCTAGAGATG
Dd432      .....
Lp_KC875348 .....C.....
Lp_KC875349 .....C.....
Lp_FR821799 .....C.....
ChangesNS .....S.....
```

```
[      4601      4611      4621      4631      4641      4651      4661      4671      4681      4691      ]
[
Dd636      AGCCAGAGGCTTGGGTTTTGGGGTTTCAGGATGTGGCAGACCCGGTAGTAGAAGAAATGTTTTTTTCATGATCAAGTAATGTTTTTATTAATCATTAT
Dd432      .....
Lp_KC875348 .....
Lp_KC875349 .....
Lp_FR821799 .....
ChangesNS .....

```

```
[      4701      4711      4721      4731      4741      4751      4761      4771      4781      4791      ]
[
Dd636      TGTCACGTGTTGTTTTATGGCTTATTGTGGAAGCTTTTTGAAATAAATTTATGATCGTAATTTAGTTGATGGTACTTTTTTAGAAATGTTTGAACAATA
Dd432      .....
Lp_KC875348 .....
Lp_KC875349 .....
Lp_FR821799 .....
ChangesNS .....

```

```
[      4801      4811      4821      4831      4841      4851      4861      4871      4881      4891      ]
[
Dd636      ATCCCCGCTGTTATATTGATTTTTATTGCACTACCCTCGTTAAAATGTTGTATTTAATGGACGAAATCATTCTCCTGCTTTAACAATTAAGTCATTG
Dd432      .....
Lp_KC875348 .....
Lp_KC875349 .....
Lp_FR821799 .....
ChangesNS .....

```

```
[      4901      4911      4921      4931      4941      4951      4961      4971      4981      4991      ]
[
Dd636      GCCATCAATGATATTGGTCTTATGAATACTCTGATTATGAAGCGAGACGTTAGCTTTTGATTCTTATATGGTTCCGCTTCCGATTTAATTTTCAGGGAA
Dd432      .....
Lp_KC875348 .....
Lp_KC875349 .....
Lp_FR821799 .....
ChangesNS .....

```

```
[      5001      5011      5021      5031      5041      5051      5061      5071      5081      5091      ]
[
Dd636   | AAACCGTTTACTTGAAGTGGATCAAAAACCTGTTGTTCCAATTGGAACATATAAGATTTTGTAGTGACGGGAGCCGATGTCTTGCATCTTTTGCGGTC
Dd432   | .....G.....
Lp_KC875348 | .....
Lp_KC875349 | .....
Lp_FR821799 | .....
ChangesNS | .....N.....
```

```
[      5101      5111      5121      5131      5141      5151      5161      5171      5181      5191      ]
[
Dd636   | CCTTCTTTAGGATTAAGTAGACGCTGTGCCTGGCCGTTTAAATCAAACGGTGTTTTATCAAACGACCGGGGTTT-----GGCAATGCTCTG
Dd432   | .....TNN.....
Lp_KC875348 | .....
Lp_KC875349 | .....
Lp_FR821799 | .....
ChangesNS | .....---
```

```
[      5201      5211      5221      5231      5241      5251      5261      5271      5281      5291      ]
[
Dd636   | AGATTTGTGGGGCGAATCACTCTTTTATGCCTATTGTTATAGAGGGAGTCGGGTTAAATGAATATATTATGTATTATAAGTATTTAGTTGTTGTCATGGT
Dd432   | .....
Lp_KC875348 | .....
Lp_KC875349 | .....
Lp_FR821799 | .....
ChangesNS | .....---
```

```
[      5301      5311      5321      5331      5341      5351      5361      5371      5381      5391      ]
[
Dd636   | TTTATTTTATTAGGAGGTTGGGGGTAGTTTAAATCGAGGACATTTATTATAATGATTGTTTCAATTGAACTGTTTATTAGCAACTTTTTTTTTT
Dd432   | .....
Lp_KC875348 | .....
Lp_KC875349 | .....
Lp_FR821799 | .....
ChangesNS | .....
```

```
[      5401      5411      5421      5431      5441      5451      5461      5471      5481      5491      ]
[
Dd636   | TTTTTTNNGATAAATTC TAAGGAAATAGACGCTTTAATAGAACAGGTTTATGATAATGGGTTTGACAATTGCGGCGGCAGAGTCTTCTATTGGCTTGG
Dd432   | ...N---...Y.....
Lp_KC875348 | .....
Lp_KC875349 | .....
Lp_FR821799 | .....
ChangesNS | ...S---...S.....
```



```
[          6001      6011      6021      6031      6041      6051      6061      6071      6081      6091      ]
[          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          ]
Dd636      TTGGTTTTTATAACGATAAATAGGGGTGTTAACAGTTTTTGTTCGCGGAACAATTGGTCTTGTTCAAATGATTTAAAAAATAATTGCTTATTCCACTT
Dd432      .....
Lp_KC875348 .....
Lp_KC875349 .....
Lp_FR821799 .....
ChangesNS .....

```

```
[          6101      6111      6121      6131      6141      6151      6161      6171      6181      6191      ]
[          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          ]
Dd636      GTAGTCAATTGGGGTATATGGTTGTGGCTTGTGGTCTTCTCATTCTTCTATTGGTCTTTCCACTTAATGAATCATGCTTTTTTTAAGGCTTTGTATT
Dd432      .....
Lp_KC875348 .....
Lp_KC875349 .....
Lp_FR821799 .....
ChangesNS .....

```

```
[          6201      6211      6221      6231      6241      6251      6261      6271      6281      6291      ]
[          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          ]
Dd636      TTTAAGTGCTGGTTCTTTAATTCATGCAATGATAGACGAACAAGACATAAGAAAAATGGGGGCTTATTACAAATCAYACCTTTGACTTATATTTTTTTT
Dd432      .....T.....
Lp_KC875348 .....T.....
Lp_KC875349 .....T.....
Lp_FR821799 .....T.....
ChangesNS .....S.....

```

```
[          6301      6311      6321      6331      6341      6351      6361      6371      6381      6391      ]
[          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          ]
Dd636      ATTATAGGCTCTTTTTCTTTAATGGGATTCCTTTTTTAACCGGTTTTATTCAAAGACTTAATCTTAGRAGTTACTTTGGGCAATATTATTTAATTT
Dd432      .....A.....
Lp_KC875348 .....A.....
Lp_KC875349 .....A.....
Lp_FR821799 .....A.....
ChangesNS .....S.....

```

```
[          6401      6411      6421      6431      6441      6451      6461      6471      6481      6491      ]
[          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          ]
Dd636      TTGTTTATTGGCTAGGTTGTTTTCTGTTTTATTAACAGCAATGTATTCAATCCGTTTGGTTYATTATGCCTTTTTCTCTAATACAAATCTAAAAGGGC
Dd432      .....T.....
Lp_KC875348 .....T.....
Lp_KC875349 .....T.....
Lp_FR821799 .....T.....
ChangesNS .....S.....

```

```
[           6501           6511           6521           6531           6541           6551           6561           6571           6581           6591           ]
[
Dd636      |GGTTTTTCCTCGTTAAAAGAGGGAGAGGGCCTTTTGTGGCCCTTTGGGGTTTTAGCCTTAGGTAGTCTTTTTTGGGGTTATTTATGTAAAGAAATT
Dd432      |.....
Lp_KC875348|.....
Lp_KC875349|.....
Lp_FR821799|.....
ChangesNS  |.....
```

```
[           6601           6611           6621           6631           6641           6651           6661           6671           6681           6691           ]
[
Dd636      |GTGTGGTCTTTTCAAATGGGGCTTTCGCCAATGCTTTTTTTAAAATAAAAATGCTTCCTGTTATAGTAAGTATTATGGGGGCATTGGGGGTATTTTTTG
Dd432      |.....
Lp_KC875348|.....
Lp_KC875349|.....
Lp_FR821799|.....
ChangesNS  |.....
```

```
[           6701           6711           6721           6731           6741           6751           6761           6771           6781           6791           ]
[
Dd636      |TTTTATTTAATTTTCTTCTAAAATATTGTTTTTTTTGTTTTCTCTTTATACCTTTTTTGGCTCTGCTTGACAAATAAATTCTTTTTTTAATTTTTTTTTT
Dd432      |.....C.....
Lp_KC875348|.....
Lp_KC875349|.....
Lp_FR821799|.....
ChangesNS  |.....S.....
```

```
[           6801           6811           6821           6831           6841           6851           6861           6871           6881           6891           ]
[
Dd636      |TATAAAAAAATCTATAAAACGGGGCATCTGATTATGAATTTAACTGTTGACAAAGGTGCTTTAGAGCTGGTTGGGCCCAGGGGCCTTGTTCAATTTCTA
Dd432      |.....
Lp_KC875348|.....
Lp_KC875349|.....
Lp_FR821799|.....A.....
ChangesNS  |.....N.....
```

```
[           6901           6911           6921           6931           6941           6951           6961           6971           6981           6991           ]
[
Dd636      |GTCCGCCAAATCAAAGACTTAGTGATTTACAGTCGGGGCAAGTTTTTAATTATGCTTTAGTTATACTAATTGGTGTGTGCATATTTATTTGGGGAAAAG
Dd432      |.....
Lp_KC875348|.....
Lp_KC875349|.....
Lp_FR821799|.....
ChangesNS  |.....
```

```
[      7001      7011      7021      7031      7041      7051      7061      7071      7081      7091      ]
[
Dd636   | AAAACCCCTCTTTTGTCTCTGGTCAATGGATTCTTAGTGAATTTGCCCTCTCCCTCCAACATAAGTTATTTTGAATTTTGGGTCTTTATTGGGCCTGTG
Dd432   | .....
Lp_KC875348 | .....
Lp_KC875349 | .....
Lp_FR821799 | .....
ChangesNS | .....
```

```
[      7101      7111      7121      7131      7141      7151      7161      7171      7181      7191      ]
[
Dd636   | TTTGGTGCTACAAATTATAACAGGCTGTTTTTTGTCTATGCATTATTGTCCAGATGTTAATTTAGCTTTTGCTTCTATCGGCCATATTATGCGGGATGTG
Dd432   | .....
Lp_KC875348 | .....
Lp_KC875349 | .....
Lp_FR821799 | .....
ChangesNS | .....
```

```
[      7201      7211      7221      7231      7241      7251      7261      7271      7281      7291      ]
[
Dd636   | AACTCTGGTTTTTTTATTAAAATATTTACATGCAAATGGTGCTGCTTTATTTTTTTTTTGTCTTTATGTTTCATGTTGGGCGGGGCTTGTATTATGGGAGTT
Dd432   | .....T.....
Lp_KC875348 | .....
Lp_KC875349 | .....
Lp_FR821799 | .....
ChangesNS | .....S.....
```

```
[      7301      7311      7321      7331      7341      7351      7361      7371      7381      7391      ]
[
Dd636   | ATTTGAAATTCATGTTTGAAGTGTGGGGTTGTAATTTTTTTATTAACGATGGCGACGGCTTTTATGGGTTATGTTTGCCTTGAGGGCAAATGTCTTT
Dd432   | .....
Lp_KC875348 | .....
Lp_KC875349 | .....
Lp_FR821799 | .....
ChangesNS | .....
```

```
[      7401      7411      7421      7431      7441      7451      7461      7471      7481      7491      ]
[
Dd636   | TTGAGGAGCCACTGTTATCACAAATTTATGTCTGCTATTCCTTACTTTGGGGTAGACATTGTTCAATGGGTTTGGAGGGGTTTTAGTGTCTTGGGGCA
Dd432   | .....
Lp_KC875348 | .....
Lp_KC875349 | .....
Lp_FR821799 | .....C.....
ChangesNS | .....N.....
```

```
[          7501          7511          7521          7531          7541          7551          7561          7571          7581          7591          ]
[
Dd636      |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |
Dd432      |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |
Lp_KC875348 |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |
Lp_KC875349 |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |
Lp_FR821799 |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |
ChangesNS   |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |
```

```
[          7601          7611          7621          7631          7641          7651          7661          7671          7681          7691          ]
[
Dd636      |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |
Dd432      |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |
Lp_KC875348 |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |
Lp_KC875349 |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |
Lp_FR821799 |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |
ChangesNS   |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |
```

```
[          7701          7711          7721          7731          7741          7751          7761          7771          7781          7791          ]
[
Dd636      |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |
Dd432      |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |
Lp_KC875348 |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |
Lp_KC875349 |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |
Lp_FR821799 |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |
ChangesNS   |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |
```

```
[          7801          7811          7821          7831          7841          7851          7861          7871          7881          7891          ]
[
Dd636      |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |
Dd432      |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |
Lp_KC875348 |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |
Lp_KC875349 |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |
Lp_FR821799 |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |
ChangesNS   |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |
```

```
[          7901          7911          7921          7931          7941          7951          7961          7971          7981          7991          ]
[
Dd636      |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |
Dd432      |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |
Lp_KC875348 |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |
Lp_KC875349 |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |
Lp_FR821799 |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |
ChangesNS   |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |
```

```
[      8001      8011      8021      8031      8041      8051      8061      8071      8081      8091      ]
[      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      ]
Dd636   ACAGGTAGTCGAAGAGCCTTTTATTACAATTGGTCAGATCTTTCTTTTTTTTATTTTTTTTATTTTTTTAGTTCTTGTTCCTGTCCTGGTCTTTTAGAA
Dd432   .....Y.....C.G...
Lp_KC875348 .....A.....T...
Lp_KC875349 .....A.....T...
Lp_FR821799 .....S.....S.....N.N...
ChangesNS .....S.....S.....N.N...
```

```
[      8101      8111      8121      8131      8141      8151      8161      8171      8181      8191      ]
[      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      ]
Dd636   AACCAATTATTAATTATGTTTTGGTATTTTTGTTAATTTCTTCTACTAATTGACTTTCTGTTATTTAGCAATCGAACTTCTACTCTTTGTTTTT
Dd432   .....
Lp_KC875348 .....
Lp_KC875349 .....
Lp_FR821799 .....
ChangesNS .....S.....S.....N.N...
```

```
[      8201      8211      8221      8231      8241      8251      8261      8271      8281      8291      ]
[      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      ]
Dd636   TTGTTTTAATTGCCCGCGGATCGGGGTATAGCGCAGAAGCAGGGTTAAAGTACTTTGTTTTAGGTGCGCTTCTTCTGGTTTGTTTTTATTTGGGTGTGC
Dd432   .....T.....
Lp_KC875348 .....T.....
Lp_KC875349 .....T.....
Lp_FR821799 .....T.....
ChangesNS .....S.....S.....N.N...
```

```
[      8301      8311      8321      8331      8341      8351      8361      8371      8381      8391      ]
[      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      ]
Dd636   TTTATTATGTGGTATTGGGGGAATGTACATCTGGCATATCTAGATCTAATTATTAACTCGAAACAACTTTTTCGGATGTCTGTCTCCGGTCCGGGTAT
Dd432   .....A.....
Lp_KC875348 .....A.....
Lp_KC875349 .....A.....
Lp_FR821799 .....A.....
ChangesNS .....S.....S.....N.N...
```

```
[      8401      8411      8421      8431      8441      8451      8461      8471      8481      8491      ]
[      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      ]
Dd636   ATTTTAATTTAGGGGCCCTTTTTTTTAAATTTGCTGTGCTCCTTTTCATATGTGGGCTCCAGATGTATATGAAGGAGCCCCAACAAAATTGTTTTAT
Dd432   .....
Lp_KC875348 .....
Lp_KC875349 .....
Lp_FR821799 .....
ChangesNS .....S.....S.....N.N...
```

```
[      8501      8511      8521      8531      8541      8551      8561      8571      8581      8591      ]
[
Dd636      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |
Dd432      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |
Lp_KC875348 |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |
Lp_KC875349 |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |
Lp_FR821799 |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |
ChangesNS   |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |
```

```
[      8601      8611      8621      8631      8641      8651      8661      8671      8681      8691      ]
[
Dd636      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |
Dd432      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |
Lp_KC875348 |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |
Lp_KC875349 |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |
Lp_FR821799 |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |
ChangesNS   |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |
```

```
[      8701      8711      8721      8731      8741      8751      8761      8771      8781      8791      ]
[
Dd636      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |
Dd432      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |
Lp_KC875348 |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |
Lp_KC875349 |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |
Lp_FR821799 |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |
ChangesNS   |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |
```

```
[      8801      8811      8821      8831      8841      8851      8861      8871      8881      8891      ]
[
Dd636      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |
Dd432      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |
Lp_KC875348 |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |
Lp_KC875349 |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |
Lp_FR821799 |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |
ChangesNS   |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |
```

```
[      8901      8911      8921      8931      8941      8951      8961      8971      8981      8991      ]
[
Dd636      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |
Dd432      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |
Lp_KC875348 |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |
Lp_KC875349 |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |
Lp_FR821799 |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |
ChangesNS   |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |
```

```
[          9001      9011      9021      9031      9041      9051      9061      9071      9081      9091      ]
[          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          ]
Dd636      TATTATGTTAGAATTGTCAAAATACTTTTTTTTCAAAAAAACTCTTATCTTTTAATTACGATAAAAAGCTCTAAGAAAAGAATTACACTTAAATTTTAAAA
Dd432      .....
Lp_KC875348 .....
Lp_KC875349 .....
Lp_FR821799 .....
ChangesNS  .....
```

```
[          9101      9111      9121      9131      9141      9151      9161      9171      9181      9191      ]
[          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          ]
Dd636      AAGTCTTTTTGGTTGGTCTTTGTCTTTATTTTATTCTGTTTCTTTTTGTGGCTCCTCATTAGGTTTTTTTTTGGCTTCTCAAACAATAATGATATTGTT
Dd432      .....
Lp_KC875348 .....
Lp_KC875349 .....
Lp_FR821799 .....
ChangesNS  .....C.....N.....
```

```
[          9201      9211      9221      9231      9241      9251      9261      9271      9281      9291      ]
[          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          ]
Dd636      TTTTGGGGCAATTGGTTCCTGGGATAATGGTTATTTCTGCATTAAACCTGTATTTTCTCTTTTTTGATTGGTTATCGTTTTTATTAATCTGCAGTTTTT
Dd432      .....Y.....Y.....
Lp_KC875348 .....
Lp_KC875349 .....
Lp_FR821799 .....
ChangesNS  .....S.....C.....N.....
```

```
[          9301      9311      9321      9331      9341      9351      9361      9371      9381      9391      ]
[          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          ]
Dd636      TTTCTTTTGTTAGGAGTTGATTTTATTGCTTTAATGTTTTTGTGGTTTATGTTGGGGCCATTGCTGTTTTATTTTGTGTTATTATGTTGTTAAATT
Dd432      .....
Lp_KC875348 .....
Lp_KC875349 .....
Lp_FR821799 .....
ChangesNS  .....
```

```
[          9401      9411      9421      9431      9441      9451      9461      9471      9481      9491      ]
[          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          ]
Dd636      TAACGGATTATCCTCCTGCTTTTTTTTAAAAGAGAGGCCGACATGACAAATTATATCCGATTGGGTTCCTTATAGGTGCTTTTTTTTTTCTGAGGCCCTC
Dd432      .....C.....
Lp_KC875348 .....
Lp_KC875349 .....
Lp_FR821799 .....
ChangesNS  .....S.....
```



```
[      10501      10511      10521      10531      10541      10551      10561      10571      10581      10591      ]
[      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      ]
Dd636  TTTGGATATTTAGGAATGGTTTATGCAATGCTTTCTATTGGGCTTCTGGGTTTATTGTATGGGCACATCATATGTTTACTGTTGGTATGGATGTTGATA
Dd432  .....
Lp_KC875348 .....
Lp_KC875349 .....
Lp_FR821799 .....
ChangesNS .....
```

```
[      10601      10611      10621      10631      10641      10651      10661      10671      10681      10691      ]
[      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      ]
Dd636  CAAGGGCATATTTTACAGCAGCAACGATGATAAATTGCTGTTCTACGGGGATTAAGGTTTTAGTTGATTAGCTACTGTTTACGGGGGGGTTTTAAGATT
Dd432  .....
Lp_KC875348 .....
Lp_KC875349 .....
Lp_FR821799 .....
ChangesNS .....
```

```
[      10701      10711      10721      10731      10741      10751      10761      10771      10781      10791      ]
[      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      ]
Dd636  AGACACTCCAATGCTTTGGGCTATGGGATTTGTTTTTTATTTACATTAGGCGGGCTTACTGGGGTAATTTTAGCCAATAGTTCTCTTGATATTGTCTT
Dd432  .....
Lp_KC875348 .....
Lp_KC875349 .....
Lp_FR821799 .....
ChangesNS .....
```

```
[      10801      10811      10821      10831      10841      10851      10861      10871      10881      10891      ]
[      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      ]
Dd636  CATGATACATATTATGTTGTAGCACATTTTCATTATGTCCTTTCTATGGGGCCGTGTTGCTATCTTTGGGGGTTTATTATTGAATCGGAAAAATTA
Dd432  .....
Lp_KC875348 .....
Lp_KC875349 .....
Lp_FR821799 .....
ChangesNS .....
```

```
[      10901      10911      10921      10931      10941      10951      10961      10971      10981      10991      ]
[      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      |      ]
Dd636  GTGGTTATTGTTATAATGAGCTTTTTGGAAAAGTTCATTTTGGTTGATGTTTATCGGAGTAAATTTAACTTTTTCCCTCAACATTTTATAGGTTTAAC
Dd432  .....
Lp_KC875348 .....
Lp_KC875349 .....
Lp_FR821799 .....
ChangesNS .....
```

```

[          11001      11011      11021      11031      11041      11051      11061      11071      11081      11091      ]
[          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          ]
Dd636      GGGGTTCCCAGACGATATTCGGATTTTGCAGATTCTTTTGTCTGGTTGGAACCTAATTAGTTCTTTTGGTTCTGTTATTTCTATTTTAGGTGTTATATGA
Dd432      .....
Lp_KC875348 .....
Lp_KC875349 .....
Lp_FR821799 .....
ChangesNS .....

```

```

[          11101      11111      11121      11131      11141      11151      11161      11171      11181      11191      ]
[          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          |          ]
Dd636      TTTTATATCTTGTGTTTACTTTTTGTTTCAGAGGAAAGGTTTTTAGGTTGAAAAGGAGGAAGTCTATAGAATGAAAACATTCTTCTCCTCTGAGT
Dd432      .....
Lp_KC875348 .....A.....
Lp_KC875349 .....A.....
Lp_FR821799 .....A.....
ChangesNS .....N.....

```

```

[          11201      11211      11221      11231      11241      ]
[          |          |          |          |          ]
Dd636      TTCACACTTATAACGWATTGCCTTTTGTGTTTAGAGTTCTAAGA
Dd432      .....A.....
Lp_KC875348 .....A.....
Lp_KC875349 .....A.....
Lp_FR821799 .....A.....T.....
ChangesNS .....S.....S.....

```